

Synthesis and reactivity of monochlorotetraphenoxoniobium(V) complexes

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Complexes of composition $[\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i,ii}})_4]$ ($\text{OAr}^{\text{i}} = \text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^{\text{t-4}}$ and $\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}} = \text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4}$) have been synthesized by the reaction of NbCl_5 with four equivalents of 4-*t*-butyl and 4-methoxyphenol in CCl_4 and characterized. From the non-isothermal TG data, the kinetic and thermodynamic parameters have been calculated by Coats-Redfern method and the mechanism of decomposition has been computed using non-isothermal kinetic method. The reactions of $[\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i,ii}})_4]$ with a variety of ligands containing labile protons (LH) such as acetylacetonone (acacH), dibenzoylmethane (dbmH), benzoic acid (benzH), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hapH) and salicylaldehyde (salH) have afforded the complexes of the type $[\text{Nb}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i,ii}})_4\text{L}]$ while potassium salts of salicylhydroxamic acid (KSHA) and cinnamylhydroxamic acid ($\text{KCnH}(\text{L}')(\text{L}')'$) yielded $[\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr})_3\text{L}']$ authenticated by chemical analyses and physical data.

Although niobium(V) alkoxide and aryloxide complexes have been known since early 1900's, they are still extensively studied for their potential applications as precursors in the synthesis of mono-, di- or trivalent metal niobates, ferro or piezo-electric resonator materials viz. lead magnesium niobate oxide (PMN) and niobium doped lead zirconate titanate oxide (PNZT)¹. Surprisingly, while niobium(V) alkoxides have been shown to demonstrate a wide range of reactivity, the potential offered by their phenoxide analogues is still far from being fully exploited. In view of these facts and as a part of our comprehensive study of niobium(V) phenoxides², this communication deals with the synthesis and characterization of monochlorotetraphenoxoniobium(V) complexes. The reactivity of these complexes towards β -diketones and related ligands and hydroxamates has also been explored and the derivatives formed have been identified.

Results and discussion

The reaction of NbCl_5 with four equivalents of 4-*t*-butyl and 4-methoxyphenol in dry carbon tetrachloride afforded the complexes $\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr})_4$ in good yields. The elemental analyses of the isolated complexes are in agreement with their stoichiometric formulations (Table 1). The complexes are fairly moisture-sensitive, poorly soluble in CCl_4 , C_6H_6 , CH_2Cl_2 but moderately soluble in CHCl_3 , CH_3OH and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$. The molar conductances of these complexes in nitrobenzene (10^{-3} M solutions) are very low, indicating their non-electrolytic nature. The cryoscopic molecular weight determinations of the complexes in $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$ show that they exist as dimers in the solvent.

Table 1. Analytical data of the complexes*

Compd.*	Colour	Nb% : Found (Calcd.)	Λ_M in PhNO_2 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
$\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i}})_4^{**}$	Orange	12.3 (12.8)	6.7
$\text{Nb}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i}})_4\text{.acac}$	Orange	12.2 (11.8)	0.92
$\text{Nb}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i}})_4\text{.dbm}$	Brown	10.9 (10.2)	–
$\text{Nb}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i}})_4\text{.benz}$	Brown	9.8 (10.3)	0.42
$\text{Nb}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i}})_4\text{.hap}$	Brown	11.8 (11.3)	0.74
$\text{Nb}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i}})_4\text{.sal}$	Orange	12.2 (11.5)	0.83
$\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}})_3\text{.SHA}$	Orange	13.4 (12.8)	0.12
$\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}})_3\text{.CnH}$	Orange	13.1 (12.6)	0.17
$\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}})_4^{**}$	Orange	14.2 (14.9)	0.3
$\text{Nb}(\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}})_4\text{.acac}$	Orange	22.7 (22.1)	–
$\text{Nb}(\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}})_4\text{.dbm}$	Brown	12.1 (12.5)	0.57
$\text{Nb}(\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}})_4\text{.benz}$	Brown	12.2 (11.7)	0.37
$\text{Nb}(\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}})_4\text{.hap}$	Brown	12.7 (12.9)	0.82
$\text{Nb}(\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}})_4\text{.sal}$	Dark brown	3.9 (13.6)	0.79
$\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}})_3\text{.SHA}$	Brown	13.11 (12.6)	0.17
$\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}})_3\text{.CnH}$	Orange	15.2 (15.1)	0.52

* All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

** $\text{OAr}^{\text{i}} = \text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^{\text{t-4}}$; $\text{OAr}^{\text{ii}} = \text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4}$; acac, dbm, benz, hap, sal = anions of acetylacetonone, dibenzoylmethane, benzoic acid, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, salicylaldehyde; SHA and CnH = salicylhydroxamate and cinnamylhydroxamate anions.

In the IR spectra of $[\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i,ii}})_4]$, a complete absence of the band due to phenolic-OH mode at $3500\text{--}3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has suggested the deprotonation of the hydroxyl proton on complexation. The phenolic C–O modes reported to occur

in free phenols³ in the regions 1260–1180, 1300–1200 and 1410–1310 cm⁻¹ have been found to shift to lower wave numbers by 10–20 cm⁻¹ assignable to Nb ← OAr π-bonding in these complexes. The new bands observed at 580–570, 550–530 and 380 cm⁻¹ have been attributed to Nb–O, bridging Nb–O→Nb and Nb–Cl modes, respectively.

The room temperature ¹H NMR spectra of niobium(V) aryloxides NbCl(OAr^{i,ii})₄, did not display signals at δ 4.91 and 5.77 ppm characteristic of the phenolic-OH proton in free 4-t-butyl and 4-methoxyphenol respectively⁴, thereby confirming the formation of these complexes. In case of NbCl(OArBu^t-4)₄ signals due to *o*- and *m*-aromatic protons have appeared at δ 6.73 and 7.10 ppm respectively compared to δ 6.75 and 7.23 ppm in free phenol. The signal due to -Bu^t protons has appeared at δ 1.25 as a sharp singlet compared to that at 1.28 ppm in free phenol. In case of NbCl(OArOMe-4)₄, the signals due to -OCH₃ and *o*- and *m*-aromatic protons have appeared at δ 3.8 and 6.8 ppm respectively, compared to the free resonances at δ 3.6 and 6.62 ppm in 4-methoxyphenol⁴. These downfield shifts may be ascribed to the deshielding of these protons due to drainage of electron density from aromatic nucleus to metal in agreement with previous reports⁵, on tantalum complexes with substituted phenols.

The UV-visible spectra of the complexes NbCl(OAr^{i,ii})₄ in CHCl₃ have displayed intense bands at ~225 and ~245 in the respective complexes. These bands may be assigned to LMCT transitions and intraligand π → π* transitions respectively.

Thermal behaviour :

Thermogravimetric curves (DTA/TG) of NbCl(OC₆H₄Bu^t-4)₄ and NbCl(OC₆H₄OMe-4)₄ recorded in air have shown them to be stable upto 74.2° and 75.3° respectively. Three step decomposition pattern from the

inflexions in TG has been observed (Table 2) for NbCl(OC₆H₄Bu^t-4)₄. The weight losses of 28.0, 48.5 and 5% for the different decompositional steps correspond to the tentative proposition of [NbCl(OC₆H₄Bu^t-4)(OC₆H₅)] and NbO₂Cl as the possible quite unstable intermediates in the respective stages and Nb₂O₅ as the ultimate residue. These decompositions are accompanied by endotherms at 94.5, 149.3°, 370.2° and 509.8° in DTA curves. These observations may be represented as :

The complex NbCl(OC₆H₄OMe-4)₄ has been observed to decompose in two steps. The weight losses of 60.62 and 18.38% in the first and second stages respectively account for the proposition of NbO₂(OC₆H₄OMe-4) as the probable intermediate and Nb₂O₅ as the final product.

A difference in decomposition trend for the complexes may be interpreted to be due to some structural and electronic interactions.

The kinetic parameters for the complexes have been calculated by Coats and Redfern method⁶ for the different decomposition stages and are given in Table 2. The average value of activation energy *E**, for the complexes are indicative of their almost similar stability. The higher value of frequency factor *A* than *E** are suggestive of the normal de-

Table 2. Thermal decomposition data and kinetic and thermodynamic parameters and mechanism for thermal decomposition of monochlorotetraphenoxoniobium(V) aryloxides

Compd ^a .	Initial decomp. temp. °C	Stages of decomp.	TG mass loss% Found (Calcd.)	DTA peak temp. ^b °C	<i>E</i> * kJ mol ⁻¹	<i>A</i> s ⁻¹	<i>S</i> * JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	<i>G</i> * kJ mol ⁻¹	<i>k_r</i>	<i>H</i> * kJ mol ⁻¹	Mechanism
NbCl(OAr ^t) ₄	74.2	1st	28.00 (28.29)	94.5(+) 149.3(+)	61.5×10 ³	1.01×10 ⁸	98.77	10.34×10 ⁴	2.52	60.54×10 ³	<i>D</i> ₃
		2nd	48.5 (49.55)	370.2(-)	13.5×10 ³	1.17×10 ⁴	-174.18	10.82×10 ⁴	575.14	-29.9×10 ⁴	
		3rd	5.00 (5.59)	509.8(-)	81.6×10 ³	4.31×10 ⁴	-163.30	22.32×10 ⁴	0.52	81.22×10 ³	
NbCl(OAr ⁱⁱ) ₄	75.3	1st	60.62 (60.03)	359.7(-) feeble	32.6×10 ³	4.1×10 ³	-182.84	11.04×10 ⁴	0.38	32.53×10 ³	<i>F</i> ₁
		2nd	18.38 (18.53)	491.0(-)	79.4×10 ³	1.9×10 ⁵	-150.84	18.62×10 ⁴	0.26	79.28×10 ³	<i>R</i> ₂

^aOAr^t = OC₆H₄Bu^t-4 and OArⁱⁱ = OC₆H₄OMe-4, ^b(+) = endothermic, (-) = exothermic.

composition process. The other kinetic parameters also account for the plausibility of the decomposition reactions.

The TG data of the complexes has been tested for seven theoretical mechanisms of thermal decomposition reported in literature⁷ using a non-isothermal kinetic method⁸. The results obtained for the complexes studied are given in Table 2. The most probable mechanism for the decomposition of $\text{NbCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^{\text{L-4}})_4$ deduced is D_3 (three dimensional diffusion : Jander equation) for both the steps and for $\text{NbCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_4$ are F_1 (random nucleation) and R_2 (phase boundary reaction : cylindrical symmetry) for the two different decompositional steps respectively.

Reactions with β -diketones and related ligands :

The reactions of $\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i,ii}})_4$ with the ligands chosen under study yield mixed ligand complexes as follows :

(LH = acacH, dbmH, benzH, 2-hapH, salH; L = anion of the ligands)

in confirmity with their elemental analyses. The complexes are fine orange to dark brown, moisture sensitive solids and are fairly soluble in common organic solvents. The low molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions of these complexes in nitrobenzene have indicated their non-electrolytic nature.

The IR spectra of the complexes have shown the complete absence of bands due to enolic and hydroxyl $\nu(\text{OH})$ modes of β -diketone (acetylacetone), α -hydroxyketones (benzoin and 2-hydroxyacetophenone) and α -hydroxyaldehyde (salicylaldehyde). In all the complexes, bands observed in the 1590–1580, 1540–1525 and 1520–1500 cm^{-1} regions have been ascribed to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O}) + \nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ modes of O,O' chelated β -diketones and related ligands which have shifted to lower wave number upon complex formation compared to free ligands. The complete absence of bands in the lower region owing to $\nu(\text{Nb}-\text{Cl})$ mode have also confirmed their formation. Based on the spectral data in hand, the suggested structures for the complexes $\text{Nb}(\text{OAr})_4 \cdot \text{L}$ are

Reactions with potassium hydroxamates :

The reactions of $\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr}^{\text{i,ii}})_4$ with the potassium salts of salicylhydroxamic acid and cinnamyl hydroxamic acid proceed according to the equations :

(SHA = anion of potassium salicylhydroxamate; CnH = anion of potassium cinnamyl hydroxamate)

Interestingly, contrary to the formation of KCl, a quantitative separation of respective potassium aryloxy occurred. The isolated complexes corresponded to the above formulae in consonance with their elemental analyses (Table 1). The complexes are dark orange to brown solids, quite moisture sensitive but are stable at room temperature under anhydrous conditions. They are soluble in polar solvents and are non-electrolytic in nature.

In the IR spectra of these complexes the bands appeared around 1590 and 1595 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ mode, which are known to occur $\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in free ligands. The bands due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{O})$ modes have been observed to move to higher wave numbers upon coordination than in free ligands. However, the bands due to $\nu(\text{NH})$ mode remained unchanged upon complexation. The trends of IR spectra are suggestive of the coordination of the ligands both through the carbonyl and hydroxylamine oxygen in these complexes in accordance with the previous reports⁷. The appearance of bands at 390–380 cm^{-1} region due to $\nu(\text{Nb}-\text{Cl})$ mode supported their formulations. Thus on the basis of the above spectral evidence an octahedral environment around niobium in mixed phenoxo-hydroxamato complexes may tentatively be shown as :

$\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr})_3 \cdot \text{SHA}$

$\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr})_3 \cdot \text{CnH}$

It can therefore, be concluded that in the presence of hydroxamate ions, the Nb–Cl bond in the parent complexes $\text{NbCl}(\text{OAr})_4$ shows appreciable stability and the replacement of chloride ion by hydroxamate ion does not occur.

Experimental

NbCl_5 (Fluka) was used without further purification and its purity was checked by chlorine analysis. 4-*t*-Butylphenol ($\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^{\text{L-4}}$) and 4-methoxyphenol ($\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4}$) were recrystallised from benzene and pure samples melting at 99° and 55° respectively were used. Solvents were made anhydrous before use by standard methods. Dibenzoylmethane (A.R.) and benzoin (E. Merck) were recrystallised

from methanol and benzene respectively. Acetylacetone, 2-hydroxyacetophenone and salicylaldehyde (A.R.) were distilled before use. Potassium salicyl and cinnamylhydroxamates were prepared by the methods reported in the literature¹⁰.

Preparation of [NbCl(OAr^{i,ii})₄] : (OArⁱ = OC₆H₄Bit^{l-4} and OArⁱⁱ = OC₆H₄OMe-4) :

To a suspension of NbCl₅ (3.18 g, 0.012 mol) and (3.19 g, 0.012 mol) in dry CCl₄ (30 mL) in separate experiments, was added a solution of 4-*t* butylphenol (8.81 g, 0.048 mol) and 4-methoxyphenol (4.58 g, 0.048 mol) respectively, in the same solvent (20 mL). The mixing of the reactants resulted in an immediate colour change accompanied by evolution of HCl gas. The contents were initially stirred for 5–6 h and then heated under reflux till the evolution of HCl gas ceased. The excess of solvent was then distilled off and the resultant concentrated solution upon treatment with petroleum ether afforded a yellow-orange solid. In the case of the reaction with 4-methoxyphenol, a little solid formed during the reaction was removed by filtration and the filtrate after concentrating to 1/3rd of its original volume was treated with petroleum ether when a solid appeared. It was dried under vacuum.

Reactions of [NbCl(OAr^{i,ii})₄] with β-diketones and related ligands :

To a suspension of [NbCl(OAr^{i,ii})₄] in benzene (25 mL) was added a solution of an equimolar amount of the ligands (acetylacetone, dibenzoylmethane, benzoin, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, and salicylaldehyde) under anhydrous conditions in separate experiments. It was then refluxed till evolution of HCl gas ceased. The resultant solution was then concentrated whereupon a solid appeared. It was treated with petroleum ether and was dried under vacuum.

Reactions of [NbCl(OAr^{i,ii})₄] with potassium salicyl and cinnamyl hydroxamates :

To a solution of [NbCl(OAr^{i,ii})₄] in benzene (25 mL) was added an equimolar amount of potassium salicylhydroxamate/potassiumcinnamylhydroxamate dissolved in dry methanol (10 mL) in separate experiments. The mixing of the two solutions resulted in an immediate colour change from dark orange/brown to light yellow. The

contents were initially stirred for 3–4 h followed by heating under reflux for another 5–6 h to ensure the completion of the reaction. A solid thus formed was filtered, washed with benzene and dried under vacuum.

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